

METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING ENGLISH GRAMMAR OR PHONETICS TO TEACHERS OF GENERAL EDUCATION SCHOOLS ON THE BASIS OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY

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Annotation. This article discusses several ways to effectively teach English and the importance of using modern educational technologies in language teaching.

Key words: innovation, information, media and technology, landscape of communication, the importance of 21st century skills

Introduction.

Today, the main focus is on the students, their personality and unique inner world. Therefore, the main goal of a modern teacher is to choose methods and forms of organization of educational activities students that optimally correspond to the set goal of personal development. In recent years, the issue of using new information technologies in schools has been raised more and more. It is not only new technical means, but also new forms and methods of teaching, a new approach to the educational process. The main goal of teaching foreign languages is to form and develop the communicative culture of schoolchildren, to teach them to practice a foreign language.

Main part.

Although it is possible to teach foreign languages at any grade level using the technological pedagogy method, it is most important to teach 21st century skills in primary and secondary grades. These processes are a time for your students to develop their future readiness.

In general secondary education schools, it is appropriate to create lessons in a deductive manner, while focusing on foreign languages in learning foreign languages through the skills of the 21st century. Today, in the educational system of developed countries of the world, the importance of 21st century skills in teaching foreign languages, especially English, is reflected in the process of research. As a result of research, it is also important to study the steps or strategies aimed at integrating 21st century skills into foreign languages. This is, without a doubt, the century we live in is a knowledge-based economy and economic competition between countries depends on these skills. Today's youth need these skills. Globalization and digitalization have changed the landscape of communication, which in turn makes the achievement of foreign language learners in their acquisition of 21st century skills in foreign language learning and use. At the same time, these students are not simply interested in performing at a high level the various language skills needed in the social sphere, situations, they are also related to acquiring formal academic skills.

In the 21st century, it must integrate serious school content with real-world relevance in demonstrating the impact of industrial and information age models. In teaching foreign languages through 21st century skills in daily classroom processes, art, mathematics, economics, science, geography, history and law, as well as interdisciplinary topics (global awareness, financial, economic, business, civic literacy, health care and environmental literacy) should be given more attention. These subjects and topics are based on three key skills: life and future, reading and innovation, information, media and technology skills. There are several conceptual models for analyzing 21st century skills, and this model provides a framework for students to identify the

digital development needs of today. In this, general skills are determined according to four dimensions: digital technologies, youth literacy, thinking like inventors, and effective communication. Ability to use digital technologies and communication tools to create, manage and evaluate information for working in the knowledge society.

Understanding technologies and their implications in complex and stable situations related to people's cognitive abilities to use information for creativity and thinking. The third dimension involves the ability to communicate clearly with others, using a wide range of media and technologies, either orally or in writing.

Effectiveness encompasses the ability to prioritize, plan and manage for appropriate and high quality. In the 21st century, one of the most popular methods of foreign language classroom language teaching is communicative language teaching (CLT), that is, communicative competence with emphasis, attention to the learner and interaction, not only communicative language teaching. has, rather, influenced curriculum design and methodology. These factors are the guidelines and techniques teachers use to create their classrooms.

Teaching foreign languages through 21st century skills requires students to be able to demonstrate knowledge, use and express information.

It requires students to not only be literate, but to be able to use it and, of course, increase their literacy within a personal information environment in order to be successful. Foreign language teachers involve students in the learning process. It is important that they develop types and perform complex project work with negotiations, cooperation, setting goals. The following methods will help in this:

developing forms of communication;

literacy, including the use of reading and writing;

online technologies;

short-term structural memorization using cooperative projects;

work alone on tasks;

problem analysis;

making decisions;

creating designs;

solving problems

In addition, to activities based on this for foreign language learners emphasizing their need, developing 21st century skills through new technological tools and semiotic forms that give them new opportunities, standard language and digital literacy.

By using narrative and media design to teach a foreign language, students can use creative manipulation of mass cultural and textual works. They can not only express themselves, but also communicate.

Teaching foreign languages through the formation of 21st century skills in students is a multidimensional process that involves each student, teacher and others. In the implementation of these processes, foreign language classes for students are formed as follows: Allowing students to learn a language - in which education is carried out in the best conditions, in an environment where students have the ability to know themselves. Effective teachers are more like moderators in that they guide students. Teachers ensure that students have the ability to learn independently and that the learned foreign language is needed in their future life. Creating an inquiry-based classroom environment where students are able to ask and then answer questions is essential to guide their learning. For example: when organizing lessons using these methods, ask students "what do you

know?", "what do you want to learn?" and "what did you learn?" students can be guided towards genuine self-interest. Encouraging collaboration is an active and vocal classroom through this method. In this case, students are in a foreign language class based on the information of social existence.

Teachers should make full use of all opportunities to enable students to learn a foreign language. Pairs and small groups are formed in lessons. It not only helps develop speaking skills, but also teaches students how to effectively achieve goals together, along with listening skills.

Learning to develop a foreign language with the help of critical thinking skills requires not only memorization, but also the ability to think critically. In order to combine foreign language learning with 21st century skills, teachers and students can work with both or multimodal communication. Prepares and supports students to participate in various discussions. On the other hand, along with the development of students' multimodal communicative competence, it is necessary to pay attention to the development of students' visual literacy. Based on the above results and analysis, the research provides the following.

1. Restructuring the vision of foreign language learning and continuing the vision to create 21st century-based curricula in schools to prepare students to be successful.
2. Taking into account the global and local needs after a thorough analysis of the skills needed for the 21st century when introducing 21st century skills into foreign language curricula and the public education system.
3. Proponents of a holistic approach to foreign language education need research, experience sharing, capacity building and advocacy for all teachers in the 21st century.
4. Using 21st century skills in foreign language classes improves learning and provides interesting learning processes.
5. To increase teachers' awareness of 21st century skills is important.

Conclusion.

Foreign languages are a means of communication in the modern world. In this regard, the formation of communicative competence already at the middle level of education and the development of readiness for independent and continuous learning of a foreign language in the future, independent self-education, thinking, solving any problems, solving these problems reflection on possible ways and leads to self-awareness and professional assertiveness.

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